

HUMANISM IN THE NOVELS OF KHUSHWANT SINGH'S TRAIN TO PAKISTAN AND MANOHAR MALGONKAR'S A BEND IN THE GANGES

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Humanism is truly the greatest national Commitment of the Indian writers. Khushwant Singh's Train to Pakistan and Manohar Malgonkar's A Bend in the Ganges deal with India's Independence and the horror of partition. They try to portray how mass passions were aroused before and after partition. Their final aim is not only to high light communal violence, death disaster, hate and vendetta, but also to show the path of humaism.

Manohar Malgonkar says about partition :

One of the bloodiest upheavals of history twelve million people had to flee, leaving their homes; nearly half a million were killed; over a hundred thousand woman young and old. were abducted, raped, mutilated.

Every citizen was involved during the terrible time of partition. No one could remain aloof or impartial. The administration and Armed forces were also caught up in holocaust. Burning, looting, killing, dishonouring women, mutilating children and animals were the order of the daily life. Manohar Malgonkar writes in A Bend in the Ganges :

The entire land was being spluttered by the blood of its citizens, blistered and disfigured with the fiers of religious hatred; it roads were glutted with enough dead bodies to satisfy the ghouls of a major war. (P-332)

Train to Pakistan originally titled as Mano Majra and presents a tragic tale of partition period of Indian History. Partition had its great impact on the community in general and the individuals in particular. As Khushwant Singh says.

The riots had become a rout. By the summer of 1947, when the creation of the new state of Pakistan was formerly announced, ten million people - Muslims and Hindu and Sikhs were in flight. By the time the mensoon broke, almost a million were dead, and all of northern India was in arms, in terror, or in hiding. (P-10)

Khushwant Singh is always purposive in his literary writing and meaningful in the present society of social and moral disintegration. He has deep faith on human values. It is his love for humanity which inspires him to write. He has a keen eye for details and a vision of life which has been sustaining him and his work. In Train to Pakistan, Khushwant Singh emphasises on the fundamental human aspects.

Lala Ram Lal, the money lender was bruttally killed by dacoits in Mano-Majra after a violent encounter. On hearing the report of a thousand innocent killing in a train from Pakistan, Magistrate like Hukum Chand exclaims "Hare Ram, Hare Ram, hundred innocent people. What else is kalyug"? (P-115)

In India people may differ from one another in various (cultural and religious) ways but there is a unifying force like undercurrent which keeps them in a single tune. This unifying force is noticed in ManoMajra also. A three foot slab of sandstone is the local deity which all the villagers Hindu, Muslim, Sikh, Chirstian, "repair secretly when even they are in special need of blessing. " (PP-10-11)

Another nice example of human relationship is found when Iqbal, an educated modern youth come to Mano Majra and wants to stay in Gurudwara. The lambardar, Bhai Meet Singh replies, "this is a Gurudwara, the Guru's house" (P-47) and open for everybody. Later Iqbal asked Meet Singh that does he like preaching Chirstianity in his village? Meet Singh replies. "Every one is welcome to his religion. Here next door is a Muslim mosque when I pray my Guru, Uncle Iman Bkash calls to Allah." (P-49)

In the novel small village Mano Majra symbolizes India. And the people having different religious faith lived togther without any kind of enmity.

When the train from Pakistan arrived with dead bodies each one of the villagers made their contribution to flame the body. Imam Baksh also made his humble Contribution. The whole scene speaks volumes of the poor, innocent villagers sentiment and reflecting their religious understanding. This incident is highly moving because it took place in the days of extreme communal turbulence. Their minds were shaped and cultured in such a way that their outward religious pratices may apper to be different but inwardly they represent a single entity.

We come face to face with another moving incident. The Muslim of Mano-Majra have been bringing food to the Non-Muslim refugees, at the temple. So the purpose of human civilization can not be defeated by the evil communnality.

Occasionally one comes accross the statments of the people reflecting their mind and mentality. An average Indian nurtures love and respect for all fellow-being irrespective of their caste and religion. Meet Singh comes forward when a young villager makes a bitter comment about the Muslim of the village by saying them snakes. Meet Sing replies "What they have done to you? Have they ousted you from your land or occupied your houses? Have they seduced your women folk ? Tell me what have they done?" (P-144)

The way Meet Singh defends Muslims even in their absence makes us belive and realize how intimate and vibrant are the relation between different communities.

Hospitality is rather unimaginable but as a matter of fact hospitality is one of the rarest qualities which the Indian people inherited from their common anscetors. This has been conveyed by Khushwant Singh in a very natural way and communalisam comes as a barriers in the way:

The peasant thought about their problem. They could not refuse shelter of refugees. Hospitality is not a past time but a sacred duty when those who sought it were homeless. Could they ask their Muslims to go? Quite emphatically not: (P-145)

The very feeling of 'Sacred duty' has been uniquely justified in the above situation. Then there is an emotional scene which is capable of moving hearts;

Imam Baksh wiped a tear from his eyes and blew his nose in them of his shirt. What have we to do with Pakistan? We have lived amongst you as brothers. Imam Baksh Broke down. Meet Singh clasped him in his arms and began to sob. Several of the people started crying quietly and blowing their noses. (P-147)

The parting scene fo the villagers is very painful Sikh and Muslims villagers fell into each other's arms and wept like children.

The love story of Nooran and Jugga is highly symbolic. Juggut Singh is a criminal 'Badmas not in Mano Majra. He has affair with the girl Nooran, a Muslim weaver's daughter. And this is the only cause which makes him rooted to village. The Sub Inspector reports Jugga has a liasion;

With the girl, Nooran, a Muslim Weaver's daughter. She is dark but her eyes are darker. She certainly keeps Jugga in the village and no one dares to say word against the Muslims. Her blind father is the Mullah of the Mosque. (P-34)

Jugga was in jail, police intentionally chained him for the murder of Lala Ram Lal. But the point of Inspector 'No one dares say a word against Muslims.' makes up and inspires Magistrate Hukum Chand to release Juggut Singh from the jail on the fateful night of the Muslim refugees transportation to Pakistan. He did so only to save the Muslim refugees and also to save the dancing girl Hassena. Juggut Singh realises that the attack on the refugees train must mean death of Nooran. The rough Juggat Singh of the village, prevent the attack at the cost of his own life to save his beloved Nooran who was carrying his own child in her womb and the other by cutting the rope to pieces paving the way for safe passage to the passengers. He reaches the rope that has been fixed up across bridge just above the height of railway carriages: The rope has been cut in sherds only a thin tough straind remained. He went at it with the kinife, and then with his teeth. The engine was almost on him. There was a volley of shots. The man shivered and collapsed. The rope snapped in the centre as he fell. The train went over him, and went on to Pakistan. (P-207)

The sacrifice of Juggut Singh, intends to inform that the over powering urge of violence in men may be only resisted by the humanising force of love. Juggut Singh's love for Nooran transcends to the level of sublimity. It is love which a criminal like Juggut Singh transforms and finds his real fulfilment of life. It is his love which gives him inner strength and moral strength to risk his life for his love, Nooran. Through the sacrifice he realises his real self. His personal love for Nooran transcends from personal to universal. Love gives strength and courage to face the evil power and transform a criminal into humanist. Khushwant Singh tries to establish the idea of love as an antidote agaist violence. V.A. Shanane comments that Train to Pakistan as humanistic novel and the novelist's faith in man, "It is a creative rendering of the real, and it reaffirms the novelist's faith in man and renews his anowed allegiance to the humanistic ideal." (P-104)

On the other hand, Manohar Malgonkar introduces a domestic tale of two characters, Devidayal and Gian Talwar, against the background of the ten years of freedom struggle. In this novel the writer shows how gradually, communal poision diverted the lives of freedom fighters like Shafi Ushman and converted into communal extremist. Gian Talwar and Debidayal, adopt non-violence and violence as a definite way of life and finally they realize the absurdity of their abstract principle.

The novel starts with their terrorist movement and ends with the communal riots of the post-partition period. Malgonkar here depicts man's inner urge of violence as in the novel revolutionary

Basu says " Would you remain non-violent if some one threw acid at the girl you loved? Would Gandhi?" (P-291).

Another character Teckchand, has the opinion about Gandhi's message of non-violence. "It seemed that the moment the grip of British power was loosened, the population of the sub-continent has discarded non-violence over night and were now spending themselves on orgies of violence. (P-333).

Though the main character Sundari, Gopal, Teckchand, Aji, Hari, Basu and Patrick Mulligan in the novel are initiated on different lines and they present a pattern of opposite colours, each and every character, violent or non-violent, is exposed to the horrors of violence. How they face violence and what self realization dawns upon them is a matter of analysis. Regarding violence, Amur Says:

The major pre-occupation of Malgonkar's novels in this reality of violence which reveals itself to character as different from each other as Shafi, Gian and Teckchand. For Shafi, the revolutionary, as to the other freedom fighters like Debidayal and Basu, non-violence is the philosophy of the Sheep a creed for crowd, Gian begins as a disciple of Gandhi but it does not take him much time to see that his light hearted acceptance of the creed of non-violence does not mean much that it could not serve him as a philosophy of life. (P-104)

In A Bend in the Ganges, Gian Talwar, Debidayal and Shafi Usman all Suffer owing to violence, though each and every individual holds a different attitude towards life.

Gian is complex character and a man of conflict. He knows very well about his weakness and wants to get fulfillment in life. At the beginning of the novel, Gian is represented as a follower of Gandhism and perhaps he was governed by vanity. In the domestic fight Hari, his brother boldly faces the challenges of Vishnu Dutt and his men but he feels Weak and trembling. The cold hard pebble of fear is within himself "he wished to hang back, to run away, to leave this, evil place and never to see it again. This was not his fight, it was Hari's, their father's, grandfather's, Dada's "(P-48).

Obviously his thoughts point to him cowardice and he fails to discharge his duty at a crucial moment when Vishnu Dutt murders Hari. Later Gian conscious about himself and questions himself - "was that why he has embraced the philosophy of non-violence without question from physical cowardice, not from courage. Was his non-violence merely that of the rabbit refusing to confront the hound?" (P-50). He is confused after facing the harsh reality and thinks that non-violence is a political expedient in the struggle against the British. It could not serve as a philosophy of life itself. So quickly he leaves the path of non-violence. He kills Vishnu Dutt, the murderer of his brother with the same axe which Vishnu Dutt killed his brother Hari.

Gian Talwar's later life in Andaman and in India is "a bundle of lies and series of deceitful deeds." (P-155) He appears as " typical youth of India, vacillating, always seeking new anchors, new directions, devoid of any basic convictions" (P-155)

As Debidayal says to him:

.....you are far worse than Balbahadur because he at least is openly hostile- you spout truth and non-violence; you are the sort of man through whom men like Mulligan rule our country, keeps us enslaved: you are a slave working for the masters, proud of the service he renders, hankering after the rewards. (P-198)

Gian Talwar's tempted and violent nature can be seen in his act of cutting through the neck of the big Ramoshi Ghasita's corpse to get the gold sovereigns from his Khobri" without any scruples.

When the Japanese captured the Andamans, he escapes to India by the help of Mulligan and he becomes Maruti Rao for sometime, and later Gian Joshi.

In Bombay Gian gets attracted to Sundari and at the sametime Sundari feels too. Later on they are involved in a pathological relationship. He opens his heart to Sundari and discloses his identity because he wants to come out from his false self to affirm his love. Knowing the reality Sundari insults his love, rejects him with hate by calling him 'Male Whore' But love transforms him as he says " I had just begun to believe in myself, taking Courage in the fact that some where ... you have now destroyed that faith (P-330).

Perhaps that Something is his genuine feeling of love for Sundari. He justifies it when the communal riots breaks out. He goes to Duriyabad to rescue Sundari, Teckchand and his wife held up in the riots. When Sundari accuses him of some "Selfish motive" and discounts his love, he is able to face her.

"Since we are talking about my degradation, may I tell you that is partyly reason why I have come?.... Gian affirms his determination: To try and prove, if only to myself, that here can be some good in the weakest human beings... don't you see that I am trying to make up (PP-351-52)

The pure unselfish love turns the weak person Gian into a strong one and provides him moral identity also. Gian stays on their house and tries to rescue them from Shafi who comes to attack them. Sundari's mother is killed and Sundari Kills Shafi with the idol of Shiva. Gian escorts them and manages to the convey.

Malgonkar builds up Debidayal as a parallel to Gian. Debidayal is a symbol of violence. His mother's molestation by a British soldier pushes him to the path of violence. He joins the group of angry young men called the freedom fighters under the leadership of Shafi Usman who has lost his innocent father in the Jallianawala Bagh incident. Though his father is wealthy person, he seeks fulfilment in terrorist activities. When he destroys the British plane his face assumes "an almost frightening malevolence, as though he were gripped by the joy of some secret fulfilment much greater than the mere burning of a plane". (P-82)

His rigid unchanged spirit is noticed in the Andaman jail also. He refuses to salaam his British masters in the jails.

All he wanted was to go back and finish his interrupted work will the sunrise of their freedom, as Shafi had described it that day, to join hands with the other in the ceaseless fight against the Raaj. (PP-159-60)

He comes back to India to act as an agent for the Japanese and to prepare grounds for the Japanese march to India. He realizes that the Japanese were ruthless overbearing and cruel -far more cruel than the British could ever be.

He joins a tea company as Kaluram in Assam and leads a passive life from politics. Now he changes his attitude.

He wondered whether all the exposure to what Gandhi had described as man's inhumanity to man had converted him to his doctrine of non-violence? Or was it just his feeling of repulsion against his fellow Indian, men like Shafi the Brigadier and Gian Talwar, that had made his spirit cruddle? (P-268)

Debidayal has made journey from violence to love. To take revenge from Shafi Usman, Debidayal buys his girl Mamtaz from the brothel. When Shafi throws an acid bulb at her, he rescues her at great risk to his life. Gradually Devidayal gets emotional to Mumtaz and their master slave relationship turns into man and wife with humanising power of love. The tough circumstances and the personal experience of the great humanising force in the innocent love of Mumtaz ultimately transform him and gets fulfillment of life. Finally Debidayal is murdered by the violent communal frantics. In this episode, there is great contrast of the two forces anti-human violence and human love:

Surrenders himself to the pain not knowing what she was trying to tell him, but taking a childish pathetic consolation in the fact that she wanted to be with him wherever he is now going; go with him as she had always wanted to go wherever he want (P-369).

Both Gian and Debidayal with their contrasting natures and conflicting ways come to realize the same redeeming factor, affirmation through love. Here Malgonkar discredits non-violence. Through the weak character of Gian. The critic accuses him of being biased and influenced by his own personal predilections in focusing only on the superficial aspect of non-violence. It demands a great heroism than violence itself, but Malgankar does not appreciate violence as a way of life. In the death of Debidayal, Malgonkar shows the self consuming nature of violence. Ultimately the affirmation is in the value of love..

A Bend in the Ganges like Train to Pakistan affirms the value of love as transcending all barriers, against the background of horrid communal riots. Khushwant Singh and Manohar Malgonkar, both protest against violence, bloodshed and hatred. But their way of approach is different and it gives a new dimension to literature. Their protest is not merely a physical phenomenon but a continuous process of human civilizaiton. In Train to Pakistan and A Bend in the Ganges, love in respect of time or society as writers present in the novels. In Train to Pakistan, love between Juggut Singh and Nooran (Sikh and Muslim) still exists in the Violent days of communal riots and Juggut Singh's sacrifice for his love Nooran and the others proves its greatness only. In the A Bend in the Ganages, Debidayl and Gian Talwar, the two diverted souls got their ultimate satisfaction through love. This human relationship - love, has great vitality, which can defeat evil forces like hate and violence. And this is the only way through which human civilizaition exists.

The protagonist characters of the novels, Juggut Singh, Debidayal and Gian Talwar have been diverted by the evil forces of the Society. But the healing touch of love transforms and makes them understand that their path does not show the way of life. It brings only death and destruction which

has been considered to the path of beast, not of human being. Here, Khushwant Singh and Manohar Malgonkar, successfully depict their vision of humanism through the humanizing power of love when the human values were really in great question.

References

- ❖ Amur, G.S. Manohar Malgaonkar, New Delhi : Arnold Heinemann, 1973.
- ❖ Malgonkar Maohar, A bend in the Ganges. Delhi; Orient Paper backs, 1964.
- ❖ Singh Khushwant, Train to Pakistan. New Delhi : Ravidayal Publisher, 1988.
- ❖ V.A. Shahane Khushwant Singh, New York : Twayne Pulisher, 1972